

EDUCATIONAL METHODOLOGY OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION OF LANDSCAPE PAINTING

R. Jalilova

Senior teacher of the Department of Arts of FarSU, member of the creative association of artists
of the Academy Arts of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *This article deals with nature of painting and pencil drawing technologies of Uzbekistan was interpreted in the philosophical ideas of the composition of aesthetic works of art. The basis of the meta-pedagogy of the creative technologies of the new work ideas is discussed.*

Keywords: *painting, landscape, portrait, domestic, historical, battle, marinistic, animal, marinistic architecture, image, figures, courtyard, flowers, artist, natural world, nature, mountain, village, city, appearance, hot and cold colors, intervals, color philosophy, mood, world, progress of science*

Having studied the traditions of visual art of Uzbekistan from a scientific and pedagogical point of view, creative painters who worked in the genres of landscape, portrait, and various compositions at the level of modern requirements. As a result of this research, the history of Uzbekistan's visual arts, its own idea in composition was studied based on the principles of a different style methodology. The idea of the work was analyzed in accordance with the requirements of the present day:

The requirements of the composition of the landscape genre were applied in practice: every artist-creator strives to achieve his goal, to find a solution to the mysterious problematic situation of the scientific division, to create an endless, long-lasting creation. The genre of fine art landscape takes a lot of time to use realist, modernist, impermanist directions rich in the beauty of nature, colorful moving figurative images in the harmony of colors, national principles and philosophical observations.

“Roses and Self-Portrait” depicts the lyrical, romantic beauty of the typical image of Uzbek girls, and the oriental image of Eastern girls in the national spirit. From the types of landscapes, the state of the viewer who perceives the village, city, mountains, lyrical, romantic panoramas is very vividly expressed. In my works, the beauty of nature, inner exuberance of the viewer, endless joy and uplifting mood are depicted in color harmony. The work “Autumn Scenery” was scientifically studied and analyzed in practice.

Scientific research.

1. The process of depicting life events and relationships to reality in the form, line, color of the landscape in the genres of the period of the emergence of art was observed.

2. The creative artists who enlightened the landscape genre in their work in Uzbek fine art began to highlight the beautiful nature of Uzbekistan in their works based on their scientific traditions rich in beautiful emotions in color relationships.

Autumn landscape composition. In this landscape, the diversity of nature, rich in beautiful colors, is reflected. It is not an exaggeration to say that autumn is the harvest festival in the works “Blessings of Autumn”, “In the Peach Garden”, “Hot Bread”, “Autumn in Yordan”, “The Cotton Picker”, “The Picker's Girl”, “Uvaisi's Composition”. It is distinguished by its abundance of special colors during the seasons. Nature teaches man to look at human relationships

through the eyes of great artists. The more we find the solution to any aesthetic problem, the deeper we understand the nature of its beauty, the more the beauty becomes more vivid. When we encounter wonderful natural phenomena that amaze us, we involuntarily shout: “How beautiful, just like Ural Tansikboev, Levitan, Rembrandt” etc. those who reveal the beauties and express the flaws associated with their perception.

A person's views, dreams, i.e. the level of perfection and perfection of beauty, are colorful and complex, and it is explained by the truth and progress of the beauty aesthetic dream of the object of the image, the true and deep meaning of knowing reality, and the high skill of artistic color representation. Among these scientists, the aesthetic dream is distinguished by its truthfulness and humanity. The autumn scenery is called golden autumn because it is rich in special colors during the seasons. I chose the autumn scenery because of its special nature, which is an important factor in uplifting the human spirit and cultural entertainment.

Studying the works of many artists in the autumn landscape, for example, U. Tansikboev “Issik kul”, R.Choriev, using a scientific approach based on analysis, in practice, he teaches to depict the beautiful nature of Uzbekistan in the bright colors of the autumn landscape with creative images.

The composition is described as the principle of the work, with full attention to the rules of style, the correct representation of the overall integrity, the color ratio, during the work.

A person's aesthetic pleasure in the winter landscape. The clarity of the landscape genre means that a person not only enjoys the aesthetic pleasure of nature, but also receives spiritual nourishment from it. The colorful colors of nature inspire the artist. With the uniqueness of the winter landscape, the nature is put to sleep by dressing the nature in a white dress during the seasons.

I like the closeness of the landscape genre to the human being and nature like a melodious melody, the wind, the swaying of the trees, the ankhor or the water landscapes in a special color, all of these people live and breathe together with nature. Therefore, in my works, I depicted the winter landscape in the seasons by describing the landscapes of Uzbekistan and observing different situations in the landscape.

During the holidays in “Khovli” and “Winter in Kuchkhorchi”, children are sure to enjoy themselves by going out into nature and playing snow games, various snow storm games, skating, and sledding. In the process of practical illustration, I started working on my work, inspired by the winter landscape, mainly through observations and sketches. The basis of the composition idea is the proportional connection of boys and girls to each other. During the current period of scientific and technical development, a person (dressing, grooming, behavior, communication, etc.) imposes a number of requirements. Today's man's aesthetic sensibility, sense of sound and materiality has increased significantly. Fine art forms these qualities and characteristics of today's man.

The artist reproduces the material world that he sees in his creative imagination and describes it in its creation.

Paints, lines and their mixture reflect all the scenes of the world, and at the center of it is a person.

The study of scientific practical research describes the connection of cold and warm colors in the process of working in the landscape genre, freely reflected and described by human vision and feeling.

Nature is reflected in the dynamics of expressing children's movements during their quiet and lively life, throwing snow at each other quickly, and demanding agility.

In the depicted landscape, the colors are divided into the first, second, and third stages.

Warm colors are taken in the foreground, warm-cold in the second, and light-blue-cold in the third. Spatial perspective of the formation of the picture is studied, as the objects move away from the observer and their hues and colors change under the influence of the air environment.

Nowadays, the level of creating opportunities for young people in fine arts, development of inter-state friendship and culture is to direct the young generation to their place in art and to develop the dream of the future generation.

Today, the painter's idea and idea of visual art in a modern way, reflecting and depicting nationality, the Motherland in various images of portraits, landscapes, compositions, observing the winter landscape, shapes the life of today's youth and their love for nature.

Spring landscape in the east, the vernal equinox lasts from March 20 or 21 to the summer solstice, the longest day to the shortest night, on June 21 or 22. In the southern hemisphere of the earth, where it is conventionally accepted to call the months of May as spring, it will be autumn at this time. Spring is the transition season from winter to summer. With the arrival of spring, the days begin to warm and the trees write leaves, the grass turns green, the birds begin to fly, and the special beauty of nature gives strength to a person. Spring happens at different times in different places. Spring is short in polar latitudes. It goes unnoticed in tropical areas. In Muslim countries, the image of the Spring landscape, vast expanse, mountain landscape, meadows, rocks, plants, and sparkling water in the valley is the basis of the composition. R.K.Djalilova "Spring in Yordan", Self-Portrait "Navruz", the unrepeatable beauty of nature is reflected in the image of an Uzbek girl enjoying apple blossoms. The composition is based on the idea of nationalism, dupi, national pattern of Uzbek dress, stylized modern style of flowers. Self-portrait It is not called "Navruz" for nothing, because the idea of the work is based on the comparison of spring holidays, the comparison of Uzbek women to flowers, and Uzbek traditions are depicted in the image that embodies Uzbek traditions, the spreading of pleasant scents from flowers into the environment invites aesthetic and spiritual upliftment.

In the work "Spring in Tashkent" the appearance of the old city after the spring fire was reflected. When describing the work, white, red, pink, colors are described on the basis of color palette. In the works "Bakhtiyar Bolalik", "Davon Dabakhor", "Shakhi-zinda", we bring to our eyes a work that reflects spring, lyrical nature, subtle, quiet beauty, its state of awakening, and gives a person a lot of joy. The different appearance of colors in nature depends on the skill of the artist. In the spring season, the awakening of nature, joy and love in the hearts of people, the renewal of good intentions in colors, the beauty of nature, and the shimmering of various flowers on the hills inspire the artist. White, red, pink, yellow, green, purple colors are used to depict spring landscapes. When drawing, it is necessary to determine the format, the horizon line, and the point of view. Then it is necessary to determine the proportions of the air and the ground on the plane, find the foreground, the background and the scale of the objects.

Composition tools (signs) of the landscape; These include location, point of view, line of sight, spatial distance, format, perspective, rhythm, color, light, reflex, compositional center.

To create a composition in this genre, it is necessary to have excellent knowledge in the fields of pencil drawing and painting. A line of color drawn from nature can be the main theme in composing an early morning landscape composition. If we want to describe the composition of the

rural landscape, first of all, it is necessary to carefully observe the characteristics of sunny, cloudy days, noon, and evening in nature.

Summer landscape. The hottest season of the year, for example, in the temperate region, June, July, and August are summer months in Uzbekistan. Popularly, the warm half of the year is called summer. Astronomical length of summer is 93/6 days in some historical sources, "Boburnoma" Spring season is called Summer. The summer landscape is reflected in the works of R.K.Djalilova in different ways. In the "Summer in Jordan" landscape, green, brown and blue colors reflect the state of spiritual enjoyment of aesthetic beauty of life. The greenness of the summer season is a symbol of calmness in a person, the process of going to nature's beautiful mountains and cool watery places for rest is the process of spiritual rest.

When we look at nature, there are many beautiful views, sky-high mountains, white cotton fields of Uzbekistan, thick green gardens, wheat fields with golden forests, clear waters of Shakhmardan, Syrdarya, Amudarya rivers and lakes, rivers and streams crashing against stones, crimson. how delightful the meadows covered with tulips are. They do not lose their beauty in every season of the year.

Depicting the seasons by drawing and using colors is an important tool for the development of creativity for a young student or artist.

"White and blue water in Shakhmardon" depicts the inner exuberance of nature, endless playfulness of joy in its landscapes.

If we want to describe the composition of the landscape of a mountain village, first of all, it is necessary to carefully observe the characteristic features of sunny, cloudy days, noon, and evening in nature.

In Shakhmardon's work "Early Morning", the atmosphere of cold colors is noticeable. Because, in the morning, when the golden rays of the sun are visible, the effect of cold colors in the scenery of nature is greater. Although the work is depicted in cold colors, the beautiful ripples in the water and its rhythm evoke emotional calmness in a person.

In the work "Family" the father, daughter and grandchildren are depicted talking about the philosophy of life in the summer season. In the work "Pilgrimage in Samarkand" the colorful coloring of water in nature was reflected in his aesthetic attitude towards nature, understanding the most subtle, typical situations, color harmonies.

The philosophy of colors in the landscape.

Green color it is a symbol of life, awakening, creativity, spring. This color has a positive effect on the human psyche.

Blue color- a symbol of dreams and hope, goodness and creativity. It is the color of the sky. Therefore, this color is associated with the spiritual growth of a person.

The blue color is a symbol of the sky and the sea. Blue is used in different nations. Blue is a symbol of wisdom, generosity, faithfulness, trust, glory and truth. In the people of the East, it is the color of immortality. Blue color is used a lot in the architecture of Uzbekistan. Domes, walls and building decorations are made in blue color.

Yellow color. In countries such as the Far East, China, Korea, and Mongolia, nobles wore yellow clothes. The ancestors of the peoples of Central Asia considered yellow to be a symbol of the sun, fire, gold, and wealth.

Europeans understood yellow as a symbol of the end of hot summer and the beginning of autumn. But yellow color has a positive effect on human mood. Decorative artists make good use of these properties of yellow.

Cold colors (brown, green, and their properties) calmness is a sign of gentleness, indifference, sadness. Change of circumstances allows a person to move from one state to another. The presence of warm colors in the environment paves the way for this.

Warm colors confidence in one's own strength, provides the ability to live an active life. People who like these colors can control the activities of others. Warm colors create a sense of love for life and self-confidence.

Conclusion In the process of portraying colors, different appearances in nature depend on the skill of the artist. When drawing, it is necessary to determine the format, the horizon line, and the point of view. Then it is necessary to determine the proportions of the air and the ground on the plane, find the foreground, the background and the scale of the objects.

On the basis of a qualitatively executed sketch, the final version of the landscape composition should be made in practice. It is done using paper, cardboard, canvas, watercolor, gouache, watercolor. For a future artist, observing life, making daily sketches and sketches on the subject will be a good thing if he starts doing exercises. Works in the landscape genre provide spiritual nourishment for a person, inspire him, bring happiness and joy to life. When describing a color, it is important to know its meaning.

Artist teaches the methods of preserving, conserving, and getting inspiration from the beauty of nature, spiritual aesthetic education, and the methods of understanding and describing the works of art.

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